

Spectrophotometric Investigations on the Composition and Stability of some Metal Complexes with 1-Hydroxyxanthone

B. S. Garg, Yag Dutt and R. P. Singh

1-Hydroxyxanthone gives yellow to orange complexes, soluble in 50% ethanol, with UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Th^{4+} , Be^{2+} , Al^{3+} and greenish yellow colour with Fe (III). It has been found that only 1 : 1 complexes are formed in all cases. The stability constants of these complexes have been determined spectrophotometrically in 50% ethanolic medium at an ionic strength of 0.1M NaClO_4 at $25^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ$.

1-Hydroxyxanthone has been used as a reagent for gravimetric determination of uranium, thorium¹ and cerium (IV)² and spectrophotometric determination of Fe (III)³. The stability constant of copper complex with this reagent has been reported by Saxena and Seshadri⁴. The present authors have reported studies on ferric complex with this ligand⁵. No work seems to have been done on the stability of other metal chelates with this ligand. In the present communication the stability constants of 1 : 1 complexes of some metal ions with 1-hydroxyxanthone have been reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Unicam spectrophotometer, SP 600, was used for taking spectrophotometric readings. Measurements of pH were carried out on Metrohm pH-meter, E-350. 1-Hydroxyxanthone was prepared by the method of Desai et al⁶ and purity of the ligand was checked by its m.p. and by the technique of thin layer chromatography. The solution of the ligand was prepared in absolute ethanol. The solutions of copper (II), nickel (II), cobalt (II), uranyl (II), thorium (IV) and aluminium (III) were prepared from the corresponding nitrates (A. R. BDH). The solution of beryllium (II) was prepared by dissolution of beryllium hydroxide in minimum amount of perchloric acid. All solutions were standardised gravimetrically. pH of the solutions was adjusted using dilute perchloric acid or sodium hydroxide. The ionic strength of all solutions for spectrophotometric study was maintained at 0.1M by the addition of sodium perchlorate. The investigations were carried out in 50% ethanol as the ligand is insoluble in water. The temperature of the solutions was kept constant at $25^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ$.

1. Brahm Dev and B. D. Jain, *Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1961, 54A, 341.
2. Idem, *Curr. Sci.*, 1961, 30, 457.
3. Idem, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 247.
4. Saxena, G. M. and T. R. Seshadri, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1957, 46A, 218.
5. B. S. Garg, Yag Dutt and R. P. Singh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (to be published shortly).
6. Desai, Desai and Desai, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 37, 55.

Composition of the complexes: Absorption spectra of the ligand and metal complexes were taken at various pH-values. It was observed that maximum absorption due to ligand takes place at 355 nm below pH 7.0. The absorption maximum is shifted to 385-390 nm at higher pH values (10-12).

Most of the complexes have their λ_{\max} at 420-430 nm, where the absorbance due to the ligand is not very significant. The composition of the complexes with the ligand was determined by Job's method of continuous variations at suitable pH values at which colour is appreciable and there is no possibility of hydrolysis of the complexes. In all the cases investigated, only 1 : 1 complexes were detected. In cases of Zn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , no complex formation was observed below pH 7.0. The wave length for maximum absorption in the case of different complexes varies slightly from 430 nm (for copper) to 420 nm in the case of aluminium and beryllium.

Stability constants of the complexes: A series of solutions in 50% ethanol containing 1 ml of M/500 ligand, 2 ml of M/25 salt solution and 0.5 ml sodium perchlorate of molarity 2M, were prepared at different pH values. The total volume was made up to 10 ml (maintaining 50% ethanol concentration) and the final pH's were recorded. The absorbance of different solutions was recorded and stability constants were calculated by the method given below.

The interaction of the ligand with the metal ions is given by the following general equations :

Where HX stands for the ligand.

The value of K_1^* is given by

$$K_1^* = \frac{(MX)^{(n-1)+}(H^+)}{(M^{n+})(HX)} \quad (2)$$

and general form of the equation by which the K_1^* values were determined is

$$K_1^* C(M^{n+}) \frac{\epsilon}{A} - K_1^* (M^{n+}) = X(H^+) \quad (3)$$

Where (M^{n+}) = concentration of metal ion

C = concentration of the ligand

ϵ = The molar extinction co-efficient of the complex

A = The optical density (employing 1 cm cell).

Equation (3) is derived from (2) as follows

$$A = (MX)^{(n-1)+} \epsilon$$

$$\text{or, } (MX)^{(n-1)+} = \frac{A}{\epsilon}$$

$$\text{and } HX = (C - A/\epsilon)$$

From equation (2)

$$K_1^* = \frac{(A/\epsilon)(H^+)}{(C - A/\epsilon)(M^{n+})}; \text{ which on rearranging gives}$$

$$K_1^* C(M^{n+}) \frac{\epsilon}{A} - K_1^* (M^{n+}) = (H^+)$$

C and (M^{n+}) (by using large excess of metal ion) were kept constant and (H^+) was varied. By plotting $1/A$ against (H^+) a straight line of $K_1^* \epsilon C(M^{n+})$ slope and an intercept equal to $-K_1^*(M^{n+})$ was obtained. One such plot for Cu (II) complex is

1. Determination of stability constant (K_1^*) of copper complex.

shown in the figure. Knowing the value of (M^{n+}) , the value of K_1^* can be obtained. From the graph at $(H^+) = 0$, equation (3) reduces to $\epsilon = A/C \dots (4)$ and the value of molar extinction co-efficient is also obtained.

The dissociation constant K_d of the ligand in 50% alcohol, 0.1 M sodium perchlorate was determined potentiometrically and its value was found to be $10^{-11.40}$.

The values of stability constants K_1 were calculated from the relationship

$$K_1 = \frac{K_1^*}{K_d}$$

The values of stability constants and molar extinction coefficients for different complexes are given in the following table:—

Metal ion	Log K_1	ϵ (λ max ^{nm})
1. UO_2^{2+}	9.97	4079 (420 nm)
2. Cu^{2+}	8.92	5715 (430 nm)
3. Be^{2+}	8.72	3291 (420 nm)
4. Ni^{2+}	6.59	4978 (420 nm)
5. Co^{2+}	5.88	8734 (420 nm)
6. Th^{4+}	11.89	4855 (420 nm)
7. Al^{3+}	10.37	4630 (420 nm)
8. Fe^{3+}	13.05	1666 (580 nm)

For bivalent metal ion complexes stability constants increase in the order $UO_2^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Be^{2+} > Ni^{2+} > Co^{2+}$.

The increase in stability with increasing +ve charge on the cation, has been explained to be due to the increased polarizing power of the cations, which can hold the ligands more tightly due to electrostatic attraction. The stability of the Fe(III) complex is highest because effective nuclear charge of Fe^{3+} ion is maximum amongst the ions studied.⁷

One of the authors (B.S.G.) is thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi (India) for the award of a research fellowship.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
DELHI UNIVERSITY,
DELHI-7.

Received, September 12, 1967.

7. P. J. Durrant and B. Durrant, "Introduction to Advanced inorganic Chemistry", Longmans, London, 1962.